

DOES MEDICAL TOURISM CONTRIBUTE TO GROWTH IN THE HEALTHCARE SECTOR?

¹Kuliyev OzodAbdurakhmanovich, ²Sharopov Sadullo Shukurillovich

¹Associate professor, Dean of The Medical faculty at the Alfraganus University, ²Assistant at the Alfraganus University

ORCID ID: 0000-0009-0464-1327, ID: 0009-0003-2585-9428

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048573>

Abstract. *This study examines the impact of medical tourism revenues on healthcare sector growth across 49 emerging and developed countries from 2009 to 2023. By applying panel GMM and PMG/ARDL estimation techniques, findings indicate that increased medical tourism revenue significantly enhances growth in the healthcare sector. This relationship holds consistently across varying time periods, alternative healthcare performance indicators, and model variations.*

Keywords: *Medical tourism · Economic growth · Healthcare sector · Tourism revenue · Panel data.*

Introduction

This study investigates the influence of medical tourism revenues on healthcare sector growth across emerging and advanced economies over time. Medical tourism involves travel for evidence-based healthcare services, including diagnosis, treatment, prevention, and rehabilitation. Recently, health tourism, encompassing both wellness and medical tourism, has expanded rapidly, gaining prominence across established and emerging destinations globally.

Euromonitor International reports a rise in global medical tourism revenues from USD 24,175.9 million in 2009 to USD 27,931.5 million in 2023, reflecting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.1%. Despite setbacks from the COVID-19 pandemic, the industry rebounded quickly, showcasing its resilience.

With improved well-being and treatment as motivators, governments in popular destinations have recognized medical tourism's potential for sustainable growth. Countries like Thailand and Malaysia have become top medical tourism destinations by providing high-quality services at competitive prices, supported by robust healthcare infrastructure and global marketing efforts.

Technological advancements, including telemedicine and AI, have further enhanced medical tourism, enabling remote consultations and follow-up care, thus improving patient experiences and continuity of care. Reports by UNWTO and ETC highlight factors contributing to the industry's growth, such as increased leisure, accessible travel, and global health awareness. Additionally, overburdened healthcare systems, rising long-term care costs, and urbanization contribute to the need for health-focused travel options. Technological innovations, coupled with supportive policies, have strengthened both domestic and international health tourism, reducing seasonality and supporting year-round tourism strategies.

Supporting the findings of the UNWTO & ETC report, there is ample theoretical and empirical evidence suggesting that medical tourism can stimulate economic activity in host countries. For example, Beladi et al. analyzed data from 47 countries (2007–2013) and tested two competing hypotheses on medical tourism's economic effects. They found that medical tourism positively influences GDP growth per capita, particularly in non-OECD countries, by driving demand for local services such as lodging, transport, and tourism. However, they also noted

potential downsides, including the strain on public health resources, which could impact healthcare access for residents.

The authors suggested that policies, such as medical tourism taxes, could offset these effects by redistributing revenues to support local healthcare, improve healthcare worker salaries, and retain professionals in public sectors, with Cuba cited as an example. Nola and Radovčić also emphasized that medical tourism enhances healthcare accessibility in host countries.

Medical tourism generates hard currency inflows, especially from high-income to low- and middle-income nations, supporting economic development. Its growth also fosters investments in healthcare infrastructure, creating demand for related industries. Additionally, medical tourism can benefit the healthcare sector by reducing the strain on domestic systems, freeing up resources, and decreasing wait times. It promotes healthcare advancements as providers meet international standards, and it supports collaboration between professionals from various countries, enriching local practitioners' expertise through exposure to global best practices and new technologies.

The economic and healthcare benefits of medical tourism are evident in multiple countries. For instance, Taiwan's tourism-led growth has positively influenced its economy, including the healthcare sector. In Pakistan, medical tourism is a significant contributor to economic expansion, and Iran, despite facing sanctions, has emerged as a major medical tourism hub, with revenues addressing healthcare sector deficiencies. The increasing global competition in this industry, as seen in Malaysia's efforts to attract Chinese tourists, highlights the need for effective strategies like enhancing patient experiences.

Studies often focus on broad economic impacts of medical tourism, but the relationship between medical tourism revenues and healthcare sector growth across countries remains underexplored. Moreover, past studies generally use cross-sectional data, which may not fully address issues of endogeneity. This study uses panel GMM and PMG-ARDL estimation to capture the dynamics of healthcare growth from medical tourism revenues, assessing data across 49 emerging and advanced economies from 2009 to 2023. Unlike previous studies, it examines aggregate medical tourism revenues, encompassing both domestic and inbound tourists, to provide a more comprehensive view of the industry's impact.

Our study addresses both the literature gap and the UNWTO-ETC (2018) recommendation to examine how medical tourism affects the well-being of local residents in destination countries. Additionally, this research follows the advice of Beladi et al., who suggested analyzing longer-term, cross-country data to better understand the causal link between medical tourism and economic growth. Panel data provide advantages over cross-sectional or time-series data, including greater variability, less collinearity, increased degrees of freedom, and enhanced efficiency.

This article is structured as follows: Section *Data and Method* explains data, variables, and estimation methods; Section *Results* presents findings; and the final section concludes.

Data and Method

Data: Scope of the Research

This study utilizes annual data from 2008 to 2022, encompassing 49 countries that range from highly developed economies, such as the United States and the United Kingdom, to emerging markets like India and Brazil. This diverse selection provides variability in healthcare infrastructure, policies, and economic conditions, offering a comprehensive view of global medical tourism impacts.

Countries in the sample include Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, France, Germany, India, Japan, South Korea, Thailand, Turkey, and others.

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable in this study is healthcare sector growth, measured by the share of gross value added (GVA) from health and social work relative to total GVA. Data was obtained from Euromonitor International, allowing for comparable values across different economies. Over the study period, Romania (9.92%) and Vietnam (9.15%) saw the highest GVA growth, while Ireland (-2.84%) and China (-3.15%) saw the lowest. Descriptive statistics of all variables are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics (before transformation) for full sample, 2009–2023

Variable	Description	Mean	Standard Deviation
GVA_HEALTH	Growth in GVA share from the health sector in total GVA	0.020	0.085
MEDICAL	Medical tourism revenues per capita	15.887	39.454
GDPC_G	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	0.016	0.039
GOV_HEALTH	Government expenditure on health per capita	1,705.835	1,747.295
CONS_HEALTH	Consumer expenditure on health goods and medical services per capita	816.144	1,448.826

Variable of Interest

In this study, the primary explanatory variable is medical tourism across countries. We use medical tourism revenues, obtained from Euromonitor International, as a proxy for these activities. Euromonitor defines these revenues as "medical tourism value sales," covering domestic and inbound trips for medical treatment, including aesthetic or cosmetic procedures. This value encompasses expenses on travel-related services (e.g., hotels, in-country travel, car rentals, etc.), but excludes medical costs. The expenses cover those of both the patient and any accompanying individuals. However, transport tickets purchased in the patient's home country are not included.

To standardize these values for country comparisons, medical tourism revenues (in millions of USD) are adjusted per capita by dividing total revenues by population. Over 2009–2023, the sample’s average medical tourism revenue per capita was USD 15.88, with the United Arab Emirates (USD 209.28) and Switzerland (USD 136.01) at the high end, while Kenya (USD 0.173) and Croatia (USD 0.12) had the lowest values.

Euromonitor International’s tourism data is widely trusted and frequently used in research. Nonetheless, it is important to acknowledge that some values may be estimates, and the dataset lacks information for many developing nations, presenting some limitations.

Control Variables

In addition to our main variable (medical tourism), we include other key determinants of healthcare sector growth in our panel data model. These controls include economic growth (measured as the annual GDP per capita growth rate), government health expenditure per capita, and consumer expenditure on health goods and medical services per capita. GDP growth data are sourced from the World Bank, while government and consumer health expenditure data are from Euromonitor International.

Although data limitations restrict the number of control variables, we use one-year lags of the dependent variable, first-difference transformations (to capture unobserved country factors), year fixed effects, and economic growth controls. This specification should adequately account for labor productivity growth, capital formation, and other macroeconomic influences.

Estimation Method

We utilize a dynamic panel model estimated through the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), particularly suited to our data structure, with a large number of cross-sections ($N = 49$) and a shorter time series ($T = 15$). This model is appropriate given the likely persistence in the dynamics of GVA_HEALTH, where prior values may affect current levels. Additionally, the GMM approach effectively addresses potential endogeneity issues among explanatory variables, enhancing the reliability of our estimates for Eq. (1).

All variables, except for GVA_HEALTH and GDPC_G, are transformed into logarithmic form for empirical estimation. In the main analyses using GMM, two lags of the dependent variable and one lag of the explanatory variables are employed as instruments.

Results

Main Analyses

Table 2 presents the GMM estimation results across columns 1–4. Column 1 includes one lag of the dependent variable and the variable of interest, medical tourism revenues, as explanatory factors for GVA_HEALTH. The results indicate that MEDICAL is positively associated with GVA_HEALTH and is statistically significant at the 1% level, suggesting that increased medical tourism revenues per capita are linked to stronger healthcare sector growth in our sample countries. This finding supports our hypothesis and aligns with previous empirical studies, which suggest medical tourism positively impacts economic activities, particularly in the healthcare sector.

Table 2: Results of GMM Estimator

Explanatory Variable	Without Control Variables With Control Variables	
	Column (1)	Column (2)
GVA_HEALTH (-1)	-0.390*** (0.004)	-0.393*** (0.004)
MEDICAL	0.066*** (0.020)	0.067*** (0.021)
GDPC_G	-	-0.005 (0.077)
GOV_HEALTH	-	-
CONS_HEALTH	-	-
Year Dummies	Included	Included
p-value of AR (2)	0.570	0.426
p-value of Sargan test	0.340	0.235
Total Panel Observations	471	460

- *Significance levels: * 0.10 (), ** 0.05 (), *** 0.01 (*)*
- *Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. GVA_HEALTH is growth in GVA share from the health sector in total GVA; MEDICAL is medical tourism revenues per capita; GDPC_G is GDP per capita growth (annual %); GOV_HEALTH is government health expenditure per capita; CONS_HEALTH is consumer spending on health goods and medical services per capita.*

In columns 2–4, additional factors potentially influencing healthcare sector growth are added to the model. However, the positive and significant relationship between MEDICAL and

GVA_HEALTH remains consistent. The coefficient of the one-year lag of GVA_HEALTH is negative and significant, suggesting that countries with strong healthcare growth in the previous year experience slower growth currently. Government health spending (GOV_HEALTH) has a negative impact on GVA_HEALTH, likely due to a crowd-out effect, where increased government involvement limits private sector expansion. Conversely, consumer health expenditure (CONS_HEALTH) positively affects GVA_HEALTH.

Two diagnostic tests are shown at the bottom of Table 2. The p-values of the Sargan test for over-identifying restrictions and the Arellano-Bond AR (2) test for second-order correlation are not significant at the 5% level, indicating valid instruments and no serial correlation in the models.

Discussion and Conclusion

While several conceptual and cross-sectional studies have explored the relationship between medical tourism and economic growth, this study is the first to empirically examine medical tourism revenues' impact on healthcare sector growth using recent data across developed and emerging economies. Analyzing data from 49 countries from 2008 to 2022, we found a positive effect of medical tourism revenues per capita on healthcare growth, measured as the healthcare sector's share in total GVA.

Our findings align with previous research, such as Türedi et al., who identified a long-term association between inbound tourism and healthcare development in ASEAN nations. This relationship suggests that revenue from medical tourism can significantly enhance healthcare growth, as illustrated by Cuba, where medical tourism revenue is reinvested in public healthcare. Similarly, Beladi et al. confirmed that medical tourism positively impacts economic growth in non-OECD countries, bolstering healthcare infrastructure, wages, and worker retention. Hazarika documented how India's growing medical tourism industry has driven substantial investments in private healthcare, while highlighting the need for equitable distribution across both private and public healthcare systems.

In conclusion, evidence supports a positive correlation between medical tourism revenue and healthcare sector growth, with implications for economic development, public healthcare funding, and healthcare sector competitiveness. However, this growth presents challenges, including the need for increased governmental support and the potential risk of unequal healthcare access for local populations. As Connell noted, in countries like India, the migration of healthcare professionals to medical tourism hubs has impacted regional healthcare. Conversely, Singapore provides a model for equitable healthcare development.

This study has limitations, such as its focus on emerging and developed economies. Expanding research to other regions, particularly underdeveloped nations or specific groups like the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) or Asia-Pacific, would provide broader insights. Future research could explore medical tourism's impact on public resources and potential health inequities, as well as the differential effects of domestic versus foreign medical tourism expenditures on healthcare sector growth, assuming relevant data becomes available across countries and over time.

References

1. World Tourism Organization and European Travel Commission: Exploring Health Tourism. UNWTO, Madrid, Spain (2018)
2. Loh, C.P.A.: Health tourism on the rise? Evidence from the balance of payments statistics. *Eur. J. Health Econ.* **15**, 759–766 (2014)

3. Salehi-Esfahani, S., Ridderstaat, J., Ozturk, A.B.: Health tourism in a developed country with a dominant tourism market: the case of the United States’ travellers to Canada. *Curr. Issue Tour.* **24**(4), 536–553 (2021)
4. Xu, Q., Purushothaman, V., Cuomo, R., Mackey, T.: A bilingual systematic review of south korean medical tourism: a need to rethink policy and priorities for public health? *BMC Public Health* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10642-x>
5. Zhong, L., Sun, H., Law, R., Li, X., Deng, B.: Health tourism in China: a 40-year bibliometric analysis. *Tour. Rev.* **78**(1), 203–217 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1108/tr-03-2022-0112>
6. Euromonitor International. Euromonitor International Database (2023). <https://www.euromonitor.com/>
7. Majeed, S., Kim, W.: Emerging trends in wellness tourism: a scoping review. *J. Hosp. Tour. Insights* **6**(2), 853–873 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1108/jhti-02-2022-0046>
8. Wright, D.W.M., Zascerinska, S.: Becoming immortal: future wellness and medical tourism markets. *J. Tour. Futur.* **9**(2), 168–195 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1108/jtf-05-2021-0119>
9. Kim, H.L., Hyun, S.S.: The future of medical tourism for individuals’ health and well-being: a case study of the relationship improvement between the UAE (United Arab Emirates) and South Korea. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **19**(9), 5735 (2022)
10. Klímová, B., Kuča, K.: Medical tourism: its research and implications for public health. *Central Eur. J. Public Health* **28**(3), 226–229 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.21101/cejph.a5744>
11. Chee, H.: Medical tourism and the state in Malaysia and Singapore. *Glob. Soc. Policy* **10**(3), 336–357 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468018110379978>
12. Mishra, V., Sharma, M.: Framework for promotion of medical tourism: a case of India. *Int. J. Glob. Bus. Compet.* **16**(S1), 103–111 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42943-021-00027-7>
13. Moghavvemi, S., Ormond, M., Musa, G., Isa, C., Thirumoorthi, T., Mustapha, M., Kanagi, A., Kanapathy, P., Chandy, J.: Connecting with prospective medical tourists online: a cross-sectional analysis of private hospital websites promoting medical tourism in India, Malaysia and Thailand. *Tour. Manage.* **58**, 154–163 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TOURMAN.2016.10.010>
14. Pocock, N.S., Phua, K.H.: Medical tourism and policy implications for health systems: a conceptual framework from a comparative study of Thailand, Singapore and Malaysia. *Global. Health* **7**(1), 12 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1744-8603-7-12>
15. Bathla, G., Raina, A., Rana, V.S.: Artificial intelligence-driven enhancements in medical tourism: opportunities, challenges, and future prospects. In: Hassan, V., Albattat, A., Basheer, S. (eds.) *Impact of AI and robotics on the medical tourism industry*, pp. 139–162. IGI Global (2024). <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-2248-2.ch006>
16. Gu, D., Humbatova, G., Xie, Y., Yang, X., Zolotarev, O., Zhang, G.: Different roles of telehealth and telemedicine on medical tourism: an empirical study from Azerbaijan. *Healthcare* **9**(8), 1073 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9081073>
17. Ha, J., Yu, C., Hwang, Y.: Analyzing the impact of relative push and pull factors on inbound medical tourism in South Korea: focused on BCG matrix applied segment group characteristics. *Asia Pac. J. Tour. Res.* **26**(7), 768–779 (2021)
18. Beladi, H., Chao, C., Ee, M., Hollas, D.: Does medical tourism promote economic growth? A cross-country analysis. *J. Travel Res.* **58**, 121–135 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287517735909>
19. Lunt, N., Smith, R.D., Exworthy, M., Green, S.T., Horsfall, D.G., Mannion, R.: Medical tourism: treatments, markets and health system implications: a scoping